
**Quality assurance at the macro level: Comparing the current and
previous Scopus snapshots**

Dimity Stephen, Stephan Stahlschmidt and Paul Donner

July 2024

Editor:

German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW) GmbH

Lange Laube 12 | 30159 Hannover | Germany | info@dzhw.eu | www.dzhw.eu

POB 2920 | 30029 Hannover | Germany

phone: +49 511 450670-0 | fax: +49 511 450670-960

Chairman of the Supervisory Board:

Ministerialdirigent Peter Greisler

Scientific Director:

Prof. Dr. Monika Jungbauer-Gans

Managing Director:

Axel Tscherniak

Registration Court:

Amtsgericht Hannover | HRB 6489

VAT No.: DE291239300

July 2024

Contents

Motivation	1
Set of indicators	1
Set of entities	2
Methodological details	2
Analysis	3
Publication counts: Total, selected countries, German sectors, and Subject Areas	3
Journals: Total indexed and the number added or removed	6
Excellence Rates: Selected countries and German sectors	7
Citations: Mean 3-year citations of articles and reviews by discipline	9
Uncited articles and reviews: Percent by selected countries and German sectors	13
Disciplines: Changes in discipline classification	15
Disciplines: Changes in articles and reviews by discipline	16
Disciplines: Percentage of publications not assigned to a discipline	17
Metadata: Changes in pubyear, doctype, pubtype and items removed	17
Metadata: Missing metadata variables	20
Institution and country data: Number of articles and reviews with missing data	21
German institutions: German publications missing from KB institution coding	22
German institutions: Changes in whole counts of articles and reviews	22
Authors: Median number of authors by Research Area and discipline	32
Source items: Percentage by Research Area and discipline	33

Motivation

The aim of the report is to identify any potential changes in data between or within database versions that may indicate quality issues. To do so it offers:

- a visual comparison
- between time-series over the last 10 years
- stemming from the current and previous KB database snapshots
- on several key indicators
- for national, sectoral and institutional entities.

The DZHW already conducts quality assurance testing at the micro-level for the KB's bibliometric databases before the tables enter the production environment. This testing is invaluable to ensuring tables and variables contain the expected content. This report supplements the current micro-level approach by examining changes in key variables between the latest two iterations of the databases at the macro-level of institutions, sectors, countries, and disciplines.

This report is not an exhaustive analysis of the databases' content, nor does it investigate any anomalies identified in the databases. However, this report probes the core variables fundamental to typical bibliometric analyses, serves as an overview of the current state of the databases, and highlights changes that may indicate issues with data quality that warrant further investigation to understand or rectify. Changes may arise through several means. For instance, the database provider may add or remove journals from indices, change the discipline classification, or change how the classification is applied. The KB may identify new or decommissioned institutions, which can affect publication output for particular disciplines, or countries may implement policies regarding publication practices that can exert a substantial influence on the content published over time. This report aims to provide users of the KB databases with an overview of any potential changes soon after the databases enter the production environment, so that these factors may be considered in analyses.

Set of indicators

The indicators included in the report reflect the core variables in the database that are fundamental to key bibliometric analyses and indicators. We provide context to the selection of variables and what information can be determined from their examination in each of the following sections.

We make two sets of comparisons in this report. For indicators where it is important to consider trends over time, such as whole publication counts, we compare the databases for the 10 years up to the year for which both have complete data. For example, the latest common year with complete data for the scp_b_202304 and scp_b_202404 databases is 2022, as data for the absolute latest year in each database are incomplete. Similarly, where citation-based indicators are used, we present the time-series up to the latest common year with complete citation data, which is 2020 for the scp_b_202304 and scp_b_202404 databases. This comparison highlights any differences in trends between the databases for the most recent decade.

For other indicators, it is most useful to compare changes between just the most recent years of complete data in each database. For instance, we compare the number of publications per discipline in 2022 from the scp_b_202304 database against 2023 in the scp_b_202404 database. Changes between the years are expected given we are comparing two different sets of publications. However, this comparison can also provide insight into structural changes between the database iterations, such as the addition or removal of journals from indices, which may influence indicators

at the macro-level. Such comparisons are also helpful in identifying new or removed institutions or discipline categories. Further, although users will likely use the latest database to produce a complete time-series for new analyses, it is important to understand how additional years of a time-series might differ to existing time-series presented in publications and reports.

Set of entities

We have chosen to compare the databases at the national, sectoral, and institutional levels. The countries chosen are based on those most commonly examined by the DZHW as countries against which it is useful and informative to compare Germany. We also examine the key German sectors: Universities (Uni), Fachhochschulen (FH), Max Planck Gesellschaft (MPG), Fraunhofer Gesellschaft (FHG), Helmholtz Gemeinschaft (HGF), Leibniz Gemeinschaft (WGL), the business sector (Econ), non-university hospitals (Clinic), and combined Ressortforschung-Bund and Ressortforschung-Länder (Gov). The remaining smaller sectors, such as research associations, clubs, and international and foreign organisations are grouped into an “other” category. Individual German institutions are also examined via the KB’s institutional coding for Germany. However, as there are a large number of institutions, we present data only for institutions that have shown substantial changes in the indicator of interest.

Methodological details

We focus primarily on articles and reviews published in journals as these are the most common documents used in bibliometric analyses. As previously noted, we supply a shortened time-series for citation-based indicators to allow for a 3-year citation window. Wang (2013)¹ determined that at least 3 years is required for publications to reach their maximum number of citations per year, after which point the number of citations are likely representative of the publication’s long-term impact. As such, citation-based indicators include all citations received within the publication year and the subsequent two years.

Whole counting is used throughout the report. Although it is most common to use fractional counting, analysing variables using whole counts will still reveal potential changes in the variables.

Data for disciplines are presented based on either the All Science Journal Classification (ASJC) or the Research Area (RA) classification. The ASJC is a fine-grained classification that allows changes in specific disciplines to be analysed. However, given it contains over 250 categories, it is sometimes useful to use a higher level of aggregation to present an overview of the disciplines. As such, we also present some data on the RA classification. The RA consists of five broad groups: Health Sciences, Life Sciences, Physical Sciences, Social Sciences and Humanities, and Multidisciplinary. These groups are mapped from the ASJC disciplines based on a concordance supplied by Elsevier.

This report is automated. Consequently, blank tables may appear in this report, but they are nonetheless informative about the indicator under examination.

¹Wang, J. (2013). Citation time window choice for research impact evaluation. *Scientometrics*, 94(3), 851-872. DOI: 10.1007/s11192-012-0775-9

Analysis

Publication counts: Total, selected countries, German sectors, and Subject Areas

The count of items produced by selected entities is the most fundamental bibliometric indicator. Given publication counts form the basis of many indicators, understanding the time-series trend within and between databases can inform expectations about potential changes that may arise in other indicators. In Figure 1 we show the total number of documents of different types indexed in each database version, followed by the whole counts of articles and reviews published by selected countries and German sectors over the last 10 years in Figures 2 and 3. In Figure 4 we show the distribution of publications by RA.

Changes in publication counts over time may reflect changes made by countries, the database provider, and/or administrative decisions. For example, it is expected that the scp_b_202404 database contains a greater number of publications for the most recent years than the scp_b_202304 database due to the continued indexing of items by Elsevier past the annual point in April at which the data is cut to create the KB databases.

Increases in publications over time also result from both the continued growth of the national science systems and Scopus' ongoing indexation over time. Sharp increases for a particular country may represent an actual increase in the number of a country's articles published in Scopus-indexed journals, such as due to policy decisions, or reflect the recent indexing of region-, country-, or discipline-specific journals. Decreases may reflect the de-indexation of journals in which an entity commonly publishes or the stagnation of a sector, such as due to funding or policy decisions or the de-commissioning of an institution. Substantial deviations between databases or decreases in the current database in recent years may warrant investigation.

Figure 1: Number of documents in each database over time by type.

Figure 2: Whole counts of articles and reviews by country and database over time. Please note the panels' different axes.

Figure 3: Whole counts of articles and reviews by German sector and database over time. Please note the panels' different axes.

Figure 4: Whole counts of articles and reviews by RA and database over time.

Journals: Total indexed and the number added or removed

The journals indexed constitute the foundation of the database. Year to year changes in the journals indexed reflect the database provider's curation procedures to introduce new content and remove content no longer meeting indexation criteria. The amount of and changes in content indexed can influence bibliometric indicators, particularly if changes are concentrated in specific disciplines. Figure 5 shows the total number of journals in each database over time, while Figure 6 shows the number of journals added and removed in each RA.

Changes in the journals indexed were identified by matching the titles of all journals indexed in 2022 in the scp_b_202304 database to those with 2023 content in the scp_b_202404 database. Titles were used as all journals have titles recorded, while some journals are missing ISSNs. Titles in scp_b_202304 but not in scp_b_202404 were considered removed, while titles in scp_b_202404 but not in scp_b_202304 were considered added. In total, 2,206 journals were added and 1,615 were removed. These data may include a small number of journals that changed titles. Some double-counting of journals between RAs may also occur when a journal maps to two or more RAs.

Figure 5: The number of journals indexed in each database over time.

Figure 6: The number of journals added or removed between 2022 in scp_b_202304 and 2023 in scp_b_202404 by RA.

Excellence Rates: Selected countries and German sectors

Excellence Rates (ER) identify the percentage of an entity’s publications that are in the 10% most highly cited publications from each discipline and could be considered of excellent quality on this basis. ERs are a common indicator used to assess an entity’s performance, with an ER exceeding the expected 10% threshold interpreted as better than expected performance. ERs for the most recent years from the two databases are presented for German sectors in Figure 7 and for countries in Figure 8. As with whole counts of publications, we would expect general agreement between the databases, particularly in the earlier years of the time-series, so substantial deviations may warrant further analysis.

Figure 7: ERs, based on whole counts, by German sector and database over time. The black line is the expected 10% threshold.

Figure 8: ERs, based on whole counts, by selected country and database over time. The black line is the expected 10% threshold.

Citations: Mean 3-year citations of articles and reviews by discipline

The number of citations a publication could be expected to receive is dependent to an extent on its discipline. As such, we examine here the mean 3-year citations of articles and reviews by discipline. Mean 3-year citations (MC3) are the mean citations publications in each discipline accrued in the first 3 years after publication. We examine here in Figure 9 the last common year in both databases (top panels) to assess the retroactive effects stemming from changes made in the latest database, and the latest complete year in both databases (bottom panels) to assess potential structural changes and updates to the time-series. A greater deviation of disciplines from the central line indicates a greater degree of change in the mean citations of a discipline's items between years. The outlying disciplines from the bottom panels of Figure 9 are shown in Tables 1 and 2, along with disciplines where the previous threshold was zero. We use a threshold of a current MC3 of at least 1 for articles and 3 for reviews to remove disciplines with spurious changes due to low levels of citations.

Figure 9: The MC3 for articles and reviews in each discipline between databases, where colour denotes the number of disciplines with this combination of citations.

Table 1: Articles: Disciplines with a current MC3 of at least 1, where the MC3 decreased by over 20% or increased by over 50% between 2020 in scp_b_202304 and 2021 in scp_b_202404, or the previous MC3 was 0.

Discipline	Previous MC3	Current MC3	No. crnt pubs.	Perc. diff.
Veterinary (misc.)	0.5	3.2	318	570.3
Health, Toxicology & Mutagenesis	1.2	3.3	229	183.2
Surfaces, Coatings & Films	2.1	4.2	1512	95.6
Development	5.3	9.4	4297	77.0
Process Chemistry & Technology	2.8	4.7	1047	66.5
Critical Care Nursing	4.3	7.0	384	62.2
Endocrine & Autonomic Systems	4.4	7.0	113	58.7
Advanced & Specialized Nursing	2.1	3.2	1749	53.6
Pharmacology, Toxicology & Pharmaceutics (all)	2.0	3.1	3393	53.1
Computer Vision & Pattern Recognition	6.6	10.0	524	51.7
Medical Laboratory Technology	0.7	1.1	113	51.1
Maternity & Midwifery	0.8	1.2	301	40.6
Organizational Behavior & Human Resource Mgmt	4.9	6.6	516	34.7
Psychiatric Mental Health	5.5	7.4	2100	33.9
Engineering (all)	4.6	6.1	15774	33.0
Mgmt, Monitoring, Policy & Law	4.7	6.1	502	30.4
Nurse Assisting	1.6	1.1	141	-30.3
Critical Care & Intensive Care Medicine	11.0	7.6	3672	-30.8
Museology	1.5	1.0	50	-33.6
Medicine (all)	9.0	5.8	105501	-35.5
Energy (misc.)	10.1	6.5	423	-36.2
Microbiology (medical)	23.0	13.4	5582	-42.0
Fundamentals & Skills	2.7	1.5	338	-43.7
Virology	20.8	8.9	2309	-57.0
Stratigraphy	6.0	2.2	124	-64.1

Table 2: Reviews: Disciplines with a current MC3 of at least 3, where the MC3 decreased by over 20% or increased by over 60% between 2020 in scp_b_202304 and 2021 in scp_b_202404, or the previous MC3 was 0.

Discipline	Previous MC3	Current MC3	No. crnt pubs.	Perc. diff.
Control & Optimization	0.0	1.5	4	Inf
LPN & LVN	0.0	2.0	3	Inf
Numerical Analysis	3.8	20.7	13	451.8
Computational Theory & Mathematics	13.1	62.7	23	378.2
Psychology (misc.)	2.3	8.7	55	274.1
Mgmt, Monitoring, Policy & Law	1.5	5.2	45	238.4
Urban Studies	8.9	28.3	35	215.8

Chiropractics	2.9	8.1	30	173.7
Architecture	2.3	5.9	280	158.5
Computer Vision & Pattern Recognition	21.2	51.6	11	143.8
Algebra & Number Theory	1.6	3.6	7	127.3
Pharmacology, Toxicology & Pharmaceutics (all)	5.1	11.1	746	117.0
Fluid Flow & Transfer Processes	12.4	25.0	18	101.1
Acoustics & Ultrasonics	8.6	17.0	37	96.4
Archeology	1.6	3.2	29	94.4
Space & Planetary Science	5.8	10.3	11	77.6
Earth & Planetary Sciences (misc.)	6.6	11.2	34	70.3
Nuclear & High Energy Physics	8.9	15.1	205	69.8
Surfaces, Coatings & Films	8.9	15.1	45	69.5
Mgmt Science & Operations Research	2.2	3.8	16	69.4
Development	4.1	6.8	148	68.7
Industrial Relations	2.3	3.8	44	63.8
Agricultural & Biological Sciences (misc.)	4.8	7.7	148	61.4
Economics, Econometrics & Finance (all)	3.0	4.9	111	61.0
Developmental Neuroscience	13.1	10.5	317	-20.1
Research & Theory	7.8	6.2	20	-20.2
Physics & Astronomy (all)	29.1	23.2	1144	-20.2
Emergency Nursing	6.1	4.8	66	-20.4
Geotechnical Engineering & Engineering Geology	14.7	11.7	312	-20.4
Paleontology	6.1	4.9	43	-20.5
Small Animals	5.8	4.6	197	-20.7
Aging	21.9	17.3	502	-21.1
Pollution	26.3	20.7	1439	-21.4
Nephrology	16.3	12.8	876	-21.5
Emergency Medicine	9.3	7.3	684	-21.5
Analysis	8.3	6.5	84	-21.5
Orthodontics	8.0	6.3	110	-21.8
Medicine (all)	16.2	12.7	15471	-22.0
Internal Medicine	16.9	13.2	2321	-22.0
Sensory Systems	30.9	24.0	46	-22.4
Developmental & Educational Psychology	17.4	13.5	274	-22.5
Radiology, Nuclear Medicine & Imaging	12.1	9.4	2531	-22.5
Health Policy	12.6	9.8	1035	-22.7
Genetics (clinical)	14.4	11.1	94	-23.0
Inorganic Chemistry	22.3	16.9	252	-24.0
Immunology & Microbiology (misc.)	4.0	3.1	112	-24.1
Neurology	16.0	12.1	2478	-24.2
Pharmacology (medical)	16.1	12.2	1219	-24.6
Orthopedics & Sports Medicine	12.0	9.1	1807	-24.6
Surgery	8.7	6.5	8309	-25.6

Immunology & Allergy	28.0	20.8	5618	-25.6
Psychiatry & Mental Health	18.7	13.9	1879	-25.9
Behavioral Neuroscience	14.3	10.6	95	-25.9
Speech & Hearing	4.5	3.3	29	-26.4
Health Informatics	23.7	17.4	931	-26.5
Radiological & Ultrasound Tech.	14.8	10.9	492	-26.6
Business, Mgmt & Accounting (misc.)	7.2	5.3	98	-26.6
Obstetrics & Gynecology	10.8	7.8	1528	-27.1
Economics, Econometrics & Finance (misc.)	4.5	3.2	92	-27.3
Pediatrics, Perinatology & Child Health	11.8	8.4	4210	-29.1
Respiratory Care	16.4	11.5	10	-29.8
Statistical & Nonlinear Physics	17.5	12.3	146	-29.8
Public Health, Environmental & Occupational Health	16.8	11.6	1869	-31.2
Multidisciplinary	32.2	21.5	2552	-33.1
Geophysics	16.0	10.3	194	-35.4
Clinical Biochemistry	17.7	11.4	699	-35.9
Building & Construction	39.7	25.3	122	-36.3
Biochemistry, Genetics & Molecular Biology (misc.)	9.2	5.8	86	-37.4
Health Professions (misc.)	6.3	3.9	46	-38.4
Veterinary (misc.)	12.0	7.4	25	-38.7
Nutrition & Dietetics	12.2	7.4	112	-38.9
Chemical Engineering (misc.)	32.6	19.4	759	-40.4
Microbiology (medical)	41.6	24.5	657	-41.2
Family Practice	5.6	3.2	146	-42.5
Computers in Earth Sciences	25.8	14.4	19	-44.3
Fundamentals & Skills	5.4	3.0	30	-44.6
Critical Care & Intensive Care Medicine	16.4	8.8	763	-46.1
Community & Home Care	7.4	3.8	83	-48.2
Epidemiology	36.3	16.8	957	-53.9
Dentistry (misc.)	14.3	6.6	52	-54.2
Virology	44.3	20.2	509	-54.3
Occupational Therapy	9.3	4.0	67	-56.8
Atmospheric Science	37.5	15.8	198	-57.9
Mgmt of Tech. & Innovation	11.3	3.9	21	-65.4
Media Tech.	23.6	5.7	11	-75.8
Life-span & Life-course Studies	57.0	10.5	2	-81.6

Uncited articles and reviews: Percent by selected countries and German sectors

While ERs represent the most highly cited publications and mean citations tell us about what’s average, the percentage of uncited publications can tell us about the entities at the tail end of the citation distribution. When examining uncited publications, we expect to see a decreasing trend in uncited publications over time. This occurs because citation counts are based on the items indexed in each database and so, as the database provider continues to index journals, the likelihood increases that any publication will have been cited by the indexed items. In particular, we would expect that the percentage of uncited publications in the last common year would be lower in the current database than the previous database, as data added in the latest iteration “complete” the incomplete last year of the previous database. An increase in uncited publications in the latest year may reflect processing issues that require investigation. We present in Figures 10 and 11 the percentage of articles and reviews per German sector and selected country that remained uncited 3 years after they were published.

Figure 10: The percentage of uncited publications in each database over time by German sector.

Figure 11: The percentage of uncited publications in each database over time by selected countries.

Disciplines: Changes in discipline classification

This section shows in Table 3 any changes that have been made to Scopus' discipline classification, the ASJC. This could include splits, aggregations or removals of a discipline, or the inclusion of a new discipline to reflect new and emerging topics. We identify changes in the classification structure by comparing the number of articles and reviews attributed to each discipline in the latest years of each database and selecting those disciplines where the number was zero in one year but not in the other. Disciplines with no prior publications but some in the current year suggest the discipline may have been recently added, while the opposite suggests the discipline may have been removed or merged. Changes may also reflect changes in spelling or punctuation of the discipline name. Any changes should be checked with Elsevier's published classification structure.

Table 3: Changes in the ASJC discipline classification structure between the previous and current databases

Classification	Previous pubs	Current pubs
Pathophysiology	NA	118

Figure 12 shows the number of publications assigned to specific disciplines identified to have changed in recent versions of the database.

Figure 12: Time-series of ASJC disciplines previously observed to have changed.

Disciplines: Changes in articles and reviews by discipline

This section identifies the disciplines that had a substantial change in the number of publications assigned to them between the latest years in each database. Changes in counts of publications per discipline may reflect changes in the journals indexed, the classification structure, and any potential processing issues. As such, any large changes shown here may be worth examining.

We show in Figure 13 the 40 disciplines with the highest percentage increases and decreases in publication counts between 2022 in scp_b_202304 and 2023 in scp_b_202404. The number shown next to each bar is the numerical change in publication counts. We have used whole counting. Disciplines previously identified as being new or removed have not been included here.

Figure 13: The 40 disciplines with the highest percentage change in publication counts between 2022 in scp_b_202304 and 2023 in scp_b_202404, with numerical difference in counts.

Disciplines: Percentage of publications not assigned to a discipline

Figure 14 shows the percentage of publications in each database that were not assigned to a discipline over the previous 11 years. Complete assignment of publications to disciplines is important as citation-based indicators typically use field-normalisation to account for differences in citation practices between disciplines. As such, items missing discipline information are excluded from such analyses and so large percentages of, or large changes in, unclassified items should be investigated.

Figure 14: The percentage of publications in each database that do not have a discipline classification.

Metadata: Changes in pubyear, doctype, pubtype and items removed

This section details the number of items for which changes were made to key metadata in the latest iteration of the database or the items were removed. We look at changes in the recorded publication year, document type and publication type as these three variables are typically the key inclusion criteria for bibliometric analyses. We also examine the number of items that were present in the scp_b_202304 database but not in the scp_b_202404 database (removed items), and items present in the scp_b_202404 database but not in the scp_b_202304 database (added items). A change in metadata for a large number of items may be problematic, particularly if the changes are not randomly distributed, such as adjustments having been made to items from a particular journal or set of publications, which may affect counts and indicators for specific entities. Some changes can be expected as the database provider updates or corrects items. However, changes to or removal of a large number of items may require investigation. Notably, the documents examined are not restricted to articles and reviews, but any document type.

We identified changes in the metadata of in-scope items by first matching items between the scp_b_202304 and scp_b_202404 databases using the item_id identifier and then calculating the number of items that were added, removed, or had different metadata. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: The number of items with changes in metadata between scp_b_202304 and scp_b_202404.

Crrnt year	Prvs year	Diff. year	Diff. src type	Diff. doc type	Added	Removed
2017	2017	0	2761	1129	0	0
2017	2018	28581	1	7	0	0
2017	2019	15	0	0	0	0
2017	2020	15	0	0	0	0
2017		0	0	0	21797	0
2018	2017	241	0	213	0	0
2018	2018	0	4852	1617	0	0
2018	2019	28404	0	109	0	0
2018	2020	8	0	1	0	0
2018	2021	2	0	0	0	0
2018		0	0	0	23549	0
2019	2017	61	17	57	0	0
2019	2018	735	5	563	0	0
2019	2019	0	6940	1907	0	0
2019	2020	109	0	11	0	0
2019	2021	100	0	70	0	0
2019	2022	20	0	1	0	0
2019		0	0	0	81644	0
2020	2017	7	0	6	0	0
2020	2018	128	0	124	0	0
2020	2019	893	4	46	0	0
2020	2020	0	7539	5183	0	0
2020	2021	463	0	62	0	0
2020	2022	265	0	3	0	0
2020		0	0	0	98581	0
2021	2017	1	1	1	0	0
2021	2018	14	0	13	0	0
2021	2019	198	14	26	0	0
2021	2020	1746	1	133	0	0
2021	2021	0	6681	8177	0	0
2021	2022	2236	1	37	0	0
2021		0	0	0	148027	0
2022	2018	9	0	6	0	0
2022	2019	63	0	5	0	0
2022	2020	250	1	12	0	0
2022	2021	2617	2	155	0	0
2022	2022	0	7696	9346	0	0
2022		0	0	0	280708	0
2023	2017	19	0	19	0	0

2023	2018	133	0	132	0	0
2023	2019	634	0	67	0	0
2023	2020	2344	0	153	0	0
2023	2021	18758	56	313	0	0
2023	2022	113769	293	745	0	0
2023		0	0	0	3976749	0
	2017	0	0	0	0	12713
	2018	0	0	0	0	11956
	2019	0	0	0	0	12187
	2020	0	0	0	0	16159
	2021	0	0	0	0	20512
	2022	0	0	0	0	39122

Metadata: Missing metadata variables

Figure 15 shows the annual percentage of publications in each database that are missing particular metadata, including page numbers, journal issue and volume information, DOIs, titles, references, abstracts, and keywords. We could reasonably expect improvements over time in missing metadata, such as for DOIs through increasing uptake of this identifier, however increasing missing metadata should be investigated. Empty graphs indicate there were no items missing this metadata.

Figure 15: The percentage of items with missing metadata over time by database.

Institution and country data: Number of articles and reviews with missing data

Bibliometric analyses often examine indicators at the level of institutions or countries. Further, fractional counting can be applied based on institutions, with articles apportioned according to authors' affiliations. It is imperative for accurate indicators that most, if not all, items have institution and country data, as missing information removes otherwise valid items from analyses.

The items table of the KB databases holds a record of all available items, while the associated data about authors' affiliations are held, in part, in the items_affiliations tables. We have operationalised missing institution information here as publications that appear in the items table but have no corresponding information in the items_affiliation tables. We present in the top panel of Figure 16 the number of items in each database between 2013 and 2023 with no institution information. Additionally, items can have institution information but no country code – from which country counts are derived – and these are shown in the bottom panel of Figure 16. Large disparities between the databases or substantial increases in missing information should be investigated.

Figure 16: The number of items with missing institution information (top) and the additional items that have institution information but no country code (bottom) over time by database.

German institutions: German publications missing from KB institution coding

In Figure 17 we show the annual percentage of German publications, i.e. those where the German indicator is TRUE, that were not assigned a KB institution code through the institution coding process. Increases over time may be due to the foundation of new institutions that have not yet been integrated into the coding process. However, publications without KB institutions are typically excluded from sector-level analyses, so it is important to understand the extent of missing institution information.

Figure 17: The percentage of German publications in each database that are missing a KB institution.

German institutions: Changes in whole counts of articles and reviews

This section compares changes in the number of articles and reviews published by German institutions between the latest years available in each database. These tables can assist in identifying institutions for which substantial numbers of publications have been added, removed or otherwise changed in the latest database. They can also aid in assessing the degree of change in publication numbers for larger institutions, which may require further examination if considered unusual or excessive.

Table 5 presents potentially new institutions – these had no publications in 2022 in the scp_b_202304 database but more than five publications in 2023 in the scp_b_202404 database. Conversely, Table 6 shows the institutions that had at least five publications in 2022 in the scp_b_202304 database but no publications recorded in 2023 in the scp_b_202404 database. We also highlight in Tables 7 and 8 the larger institutions (with at least 20 publications) that had a change in publication counts of more than 40% between 2022 and 2023 in the scp_b_202304 and scp_b_202404 databases.

Table 5: Institutions with more than 5 publications in 2023 in scp_b_202404 that had no publications in 2022 in scp_b_202304.

Inst ID	Name	Previous pubs	Current pubs
813	Europäisches Laboratorium für Molekularb	0	385
6128	Exzellenzcluster Cellular Stress Respons	0	296

5829	Fakultät für Gesundheitswissenschaften -	0	279
6260	ct.qmat - Complexity and Topology in Qua	0	175
6136	Exzellenzcluster NeuroCure	0	159
4426	Exzellenzcluster ORIGINS	0	153
5060	Göttingen Campus	0	139
5471	DWI - Leibniz-Institut für Interaktive M	0	126
5936	Sammelkategorie Independent Researcher	0	122
6152	Landschaftsverband Westfalen-Lippe (LWL)	0	119
6154	Bayerisches Polymerinstitut	0	109
5293	Biomedical Research in Endstage and Obst	0	94
2827	Klinikum Augsburg	0	93
6155	Bayerische Zentrum für Krebsforschung (B	0	84
5755	Saarland Informatics Campus	0	82
5942	Senckenberg Centre for Human Evolution a	0	76
6036	AbbVie Deutschland GmbH & Co. KG	0	72
6117	TWINCORE Zentrum für Experimentelle und	0	71
4748	IU Internationale Hochschule GmbH	0	69
5957	European Reference Network for Rare Dise	0	68
5879	HMU Health and Medical University Potsda	0	66
5373	LungenClinic Grosshansdorf - Akademische	0	63
6191	Zentrum für Individualisierte Infektions	0	63
240	United Nations University	0	60
250	Europäische Kommission	0	56
5857	Berliner Hochschule für Technik (BHT)	0	56
892	NMI Naturwissenschaftliches und Medizini	0	54
6221	Global Labor Organization (GLO) gGmbH	0	54
5894	Hochschule Weihenstephan-Triesdorf	0	49
5941	Bayerische Staatssammlung für Paläontolo	0	49
5899	Ostfalia Hochschule für angewandte Wisse	0	47
5928	Zentrum für angewandte Raumfahrttechnolo	0	47
6203	Munich Center for Machine Learning	0	47
6208	Institute for Lung Health (ILH)	0	46
6215	Berlin Institute for the Foundations of	0	43
5897	Katholische Hochschule für Sozialwesen B	0	41
6238	Sozialstiftung Bamberg	0	41
821	Deutsches Archäologisches Institut (DAI)	0	40
5958	Münchener Rückversicherungs-Gesellschaft	0	40
1096	European Space Agency	0	39
6195	Nokia Deutschland	0	39
5975	European Virus Bioinformatics Center	0	37
1303	Institut für Pathologie Mannheim	0	35
5180	Korea Institute of Science and Technolog	0	35
6219	IFN Schönow e.V.	0	35

5508	EUROfusion Consortium Research Instituti	0	33
1126	Fraunhofer-Institutszentrum Schloss Birl	0	32
5886	Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	0	32
6026	European Astronaut Center (EAC)	0	31
1382	Miltenyi Biotec B.V. & Co. KG	0	30
6034	Daiichi Sankyo Europe GmbH	0	30
6210	Sammelkategorie Vereine, Stiftungen	0	30
5913	Max Planck School of Cognition	0	27
5938	Porsche AG	0	27
6159	SPORTHOPAEDICUM STRAUBING – BERLIN – REG	0	27
6250	Excellence Cluster Cardio-Pulmonary Inst	0	27
930	Leibniz-Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe (0	26
1569	Bruker BioSpin GmbH	0	26
5837	Zentrum für Individualisierte Infektiosm	0	26
5838	Nationalpark Berchtesgaden	0	26
5914	Max Planck School Matter to Life	0	26
5907	Technische Hochschule Ulm (THU)	0	25
5999	Bayerisches Landesamt für Umwelt (LfU)	0	25
6005	Facility for Antiproton and Ion Research	0	25
6123	IDeA-Zentrum	0	25
6169	Wissenschaftliches Institut der AOK (WId	0	25
6244	MVZ HPH Institut für Pathologie und Häma	0	25
6018	Deutscher Verein des Gas- und Wasserfach	0	24
6067	Institute for Integrated Management of M	0	24
6281	TSG ResearchLab gGmbH	0	24
5855	APOLLON Hochschule der Gesundheitswirtsc	0	23
5903	SRH Berlin University of Applied Science	0	23
5906	Technische Hochschule Aschaffenburg	0	23
5918	Hessisches Landesamt für Naturschutz, Um	0	23
6009	AWMF (Arbeitsgemeinschaft der Wissenscha	0	23
6137	Schaeffler Technologies AG & Co. KG	0	23
4694	Zentralinstitut für die kassenärztliche	0	22
6079	Institut für Angewandte Trainingswissens	0	22
6099	Institut für Therapie- und Gesundheitsfo	0	22
1445	Institut für Chemo- und Biosensorik (ICB	0	21
4404	Institut für sozial-ökologische Forschun	0	21
5950	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale	0	21
1292	Henkel AG & Co KGaA	0	20
5887	Hochschule für Forstwirtschaft Rottenbur	0	20
5891	Hochschule Hof	0	20
259	Marien-Hospital Wesel gGmbH	0	19
313	Marienhospital Osnabrück GmbH	0	19
1442	IDEXX GmbH	0	19

5840	Bonn International Centre for Conflict S	0	19
5880	Hochschule der Bundesagentur für Arbeit	0	19
5960	BARMER	0	19
6017	Curt-Engelhorn-Zentrum Archäometrie gGmb	0	19
6143	Privatpraxis Prof. Jonas und Dr. Panda-J	0	19
6164	Krebsregister Saarland	0	19
6187	Asklepios Medical School GmbH	0	19
6189	Deutsche Diabetes Stiftung	0	19
6229	Medicover GmbH	0	19
848	Bundesagentur für Arbeit	0	18
5892	Hochschule Macromedia	0	18
6045	Giersch Science Center (GSC)	0	18
6262	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather	0	18
696	KfH Kuratorium für Dialyse und Nierentra	0	17
751	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Anästhesiologi	0	17
5832	Global Climate Forum e.V. (GCF)	0	17
6002	Deutsche Institute für Textil- und Faser	0	17
6286	Continental AG	0	17
1384	KWS Saat AG	0	16
1457	Heraeus Holding GmbH	0	16
5926	TRON - Translationale Onkologie an der U	0	16
6012	Bonn-Aachen International Center for Inf	0	16
6144	Cluster of Excellence RESOLV	0	16
6156	Geoverbund ABC/J	0	16
5744	Endokrinologiepraxis am Stuttgarter Plat	0	15
5883	Hochschule des Bundes für öffentliche Ve	0	15
5915	Max Planck School of Photonics	0	15
5979	Alexander von Humboldt-Stiftung	0	15
6066	Institut der deutschen Wirtschaft Köln e	0	15
6161	Science-Consulting in Diabetes GmbH	0	15
6253	spectrumK GmbH	0	15
703	Institut für Qualität und Wirtschaftlich	0	14
5854	Akkon-Hochschule für Humanwissenschaften	0	14
5900	PFH Private Hochschule Göttingen	0	14
5972	Lead Discovery Center GmbH	0	14
6054	Hamburger Institut für Sozialforschung	0	14
6087	Institut für Hygiene und Umwelt	0	14
6121	Zentrum für Osteuropa- und International	0	14
6153	UKM Marienhospital Steinfurt GmbH	0	14
6194	Evangelisches Klinikum Bethel gGmbH	0	14
6259	Deutsches Meeresmuseum - Museum für Meer	0	14
4623	GISMA Business School	0	13
5532	Forschungsgruppe Soziale Neurowissenscha	0	13

5865	DIPLOMA Hochschule	0	13
5893	Hochschule Stralsund	0	13
5948	Infinera Deutschland GmbH	0	13
5954	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Urologie e.V.	0	13
6213	CUTANEON - Skin & Hair Innovations GmbH	0	13
6225	Nuvisan GmbH	0	13
6239	Berufsgenossenschaft für Gesundheitsdien	0	13
6251	WIG2 GmbH	0	13
495	Marienhospital Bottrop gGmbH	0	12
4522	ZB MED - Informationszentrum Lebenswisse	0	12
5475	Leibniz-Institut für Medienforschung - H	0	12
5845	von Hoerner & Sulger GmbH	0	12
5933	ICO Independent Consultants GmbH	0	12
6112	Stiftung Institut für Herzinfarktforschu	0	12
6163	Landeskrebsregister NRW gGmbH	0	12
6246	Experimental Pharmacology & Oncology Ber	0	12
208	Institut für Lebensmittel- und Umweltfor	0	11
530	Asklepios Klinik Sankt Augustin GmbH	0	11
852	Bundesamt für Bauwesen und Raumordnung (0	11
1121	Fraunhofer-Zentrum für Internationales M	0	11
5486	Fraunhofer-Institut für Mikrotechnik und	0	11
5890	Hochschule für Wirtschaft und Gesellscha	0	11
5952	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Gastroenterolo	0	11
6182	VODAFONE Deutschland	0	11
6237	StatConsult Gesellschaft für klinische u	0	11
6265	St. Josef-Stift Sendenhorst	0	11
6293	Amazon Deutschland	0	11
263	St. Marienhospital Vechta	0	10
858	Bundesamt für Migration und Flüchtlinge	0	10
881	Stiftung Schleswig-Holsteinische Landesm	0	10
925	Kriminologisches Forschungsinstitut Nied	0	10
5539	Deutsche Hochschule der Polizei	0	10
5611	Helmholtz-Institut für Metabolismus-, Ad	0	10
5745	Saurierwelt Paläontologisches Museum	0	10
5868	Evangelische Hochschule Dresden	0	10
5904	SRH Fernhochschule Riedlingen	0	10
5912	European Hidradenitis Suppurativa Founda	0	10
5929	Zentrum für Mechatronik und Automatisier	0	10
5946	Kriminologische Zentralstelle e.V. (Krim	0	10
5970	Energie Campus Nürnberg	0	10
5993	Neurologisches Rehabilitationszentrum Go	0	10
6177	ADIDAS AG	0	10
6185	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Hämatologie un	0	10

6230	Charles River Deutschland	0	10
6243	MVZ genetikum® GmbH	0	10
197	Staatliche Museen zu Berlin	0	9
538	Marienhospital Aachen	0	9
744	DRF Stiftung Luftrettung gemeinnützige A	0	9
807	Flugmedizinisches Institut der Luftwaffe	0	9
908	Landeslabor Berlin-Brandenburg	0	9
4560	Bundesdeutsche Arbeitsgemeinschaft für V	0	9
4695	Zentrum für Pränataldiagnostik und Human	0	9
5389	Framatome GmbH	0	9
5839	Berlin Center for Genomics in Biodiversi	0	9
5844	Klinikum St. Marien Amberg	0	9
5863	Deutsche Hochschule für Prävention und G	0	9
5916	Landesamt für Bergbau, Energie und Geolo	0	9
6091	Institut für Marine Biotechnologie e.V.	0	9
6097	Institut für Nanophotonik Göttingen e.V.	0	9
6167	Bavarian Nordic GmbH	0	9
6249	Kompetenznetz Vorhofflimmern e.V.	0	9
6272	IKF Pneumologie GmbH & Co. KG - Institut	0	9
949	Institut für Biotechnologie und Wirkstof	0	8
1148	Fraunhofer-Institut für Naturwissenschaft	0	8
1243	SMS group GmbH	0	8
3865	RZPD Deutsches Ressourcenzentrum für Gen	0	8
5841	MBN Research Center gGmbH	0	8
5885	Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaften	0	8
5896	Karlshochschule International University	0	8
5898	Munich Business School GmbH	0	8
5966	MVZ Medizinisches Labor Bremen GmbH	0	8
6043	Forschungsstelle für Energiewirtschaft (0	8
6062	ifak - Institut für Automation und Kommu	0	8
6074	Reiner Lemoine Institut gGmbH	0	8
6096	Institut für Mittelstandsforschung Bonn	0	8
6104	Landesamt für Denkmalpflege und Archäolo	0	8
6111	Statistisches Bundesamt	0	8
6119	Landesbetrieb Hessisches Landeslabor	0	8
6124	AVL Deutschland Netzwerk	0	8
6134	glyXera GmbH	0	8
6149	AVL Deutschland GmbH	0	8
6175	TOMTEC Imaging Systems GmbH	0	8
6183	Heidelberg Materials AG	0	8
6200	Labor Dr. Wisplinghoff	0	8
6228	ADAMA Deutschland GmbH	0	8
6233	Signatope GmbH	0	8

6254	Ministerium für Ländlichen Raum und Verb	0	8
6261	Radiologische Allianz eGbR	0	8
689	Parmenides Foundation	0	7
810	Bundesforschungsanstalt für Landwirtscha	0	7
824	Bundesamt für Ausrüstung, Informationste	0	7
2691	Bundesministerium für Digitales und Verk	0	7
4663	Deutsche Lufthansa AG	0	7
5905	SRH Wilhelm Löhe Hochschule	0	7
5920	Neue Materialien Bayreuth GmbH	0	7
5995	Bauhaus Luftfahrt e.V.	0	7
6001	Bayerisches Zentrum für Angewandte Energ	0	7
6032	CAPNETZ Stiftung	0	7
6071	Institut für Diabetes "Gerhard Katsch" K	0	7
6075	Photonik-Zentrum Kaiserslautern e.V.	0	7
6108	Landesanstalt für Umwelt Baden-Würtember	0	7
6127	THE CROP TRUST	0	7
6197	Shell Deutschland GmbH	0	7
6231	Raith GmbH	0	7
6235	Restkategorie Ressortforschung Länder	0	7
426	Marienhospital Gelsenkirchen GmbH	0	6
632	Fachhochschule für öffentliche Verwaltun	0	6
882	Soziologisches Forschungsinstitut (SOFI)	0	6
889	Osteuropa-Institut (OEI)	0	6
945	Institut für Oberflächen- und Schichtana	0	6
967	Generaldirektion Kulturelles Erbe Rheinl	0	6
1304	Pathologisches Institut Koblenz	0	6
4545	A.R.T. Photonics GmbH	0	6
4707	THEVA Dünnschichttechnik GmbH	0	6
5774	Fraunhofer-Center für Maritime Logistik	0	6
5819	Staatliche Hochschule für Musik und Dars	0	6
5877	Hamburg School of Business Administratio	0	6
5989	Rheumazentrum Schleswig-Holstein Mitte	0	6
6086	Institut für Holztechnologie Dresden gGm	0	6
6103	Vector Consulting Services (VCS) GmbH	0	6
6109	Landwirtschaftskammer Niedersachsen	0	6
6148	Bertelsmann Stiftung	0	6
6162	Heidelberg Engineering GmbH	0	6
6165	Hamburgisches Krebsregister	0	6
6192	PricewaterhouseCoopers GmbH	0	6
6245	Epilepsiezentrum Kleinwachau gemeinnützi	0	6
6274	DNV SE	0	6
6275	BioTeSys GmbH	0	6

Table 6: Institutions with no publications in 2023 in scp_b_202404 that had more than 5 publications in 2022 in scp_b_202304.

Inst ID	Name	Previous pubs	Current pubs
4737	Institute for Advanced Sustainability St	116	0
5676	Springer Medizin Verlag GmbH	86	0
5483	Fraunhofer-Institut für Energiewirtschaft	35	0
5609	Deutsche Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY	30	0
1328	Nokia Siemens Networks GmbH & Co. KG	21	0
3929	Epidemiologisches Krebsregister Saarland	19	0
1264	Sankyo Europe GMBH	13	0
5753	Hochschule für Wirtschaft und Umwelt Nür	9	0
4402	Staatliche Hochschule für Musik Freiburg	7	0
5742	RetinaScience	7	0
483	Klinikum Coburg GmbH	6	0
4448	Institut für Mechatronik e.V.	6	0

Table 7: Institutions with more than 20 publications in 2022 in scp_b_202304 that increased in publication counts by over 40% in 2023 in scp_b_202404.

Inst ID	Name	Previous pubs	Current pubs	Perc. diff.
211	Senckenberg Museum für Naturkunde Görlitz	26	255	880.8
4400	Centrum für Integrierte Onkologie Köln B	74	365	393.2
587	Technische Hochschule Lübeck (THL)	29	98	237.9
845	Max Rubner-Institut (MRI), Bundesforsch	35	107	205.7
4159	Fraunhofer-Institut für Windenergiesyste	21	58	176.2
1572	Bruker Corporation	31	84	171.0
396	HELIOS Kliniken GmbH	378	978	158.7
794	Paul-Ehrlich-Institut - Bundesinstitut f	43	111	158.1
621	Hochschule Hannover	25	64	156.0
856	Bundesanstalt für Arbeitsschutz und Arbe	33	82	148.5
1971	Technische Hochschule Köln	52	124	138.5
573	Technische Hochschule Nürnberg Georg Sim	29	66	127.6
1359	Merck KGaA	122	269	120.5
584	Hochschule Mannheim	46	94	104.3
662	Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	29	59	103.4
1146	Fraunhofer-Institut für Produktionstechn	91	182	100.0
5771	Max-Planck-Institut für biologische Inte	22	44	100.0
1031	Max-Planck-Institut für Bildungsforschun	237	472	99.2
50	Leibniz-Institut für Experimentelle Viro	51	99	94.1
835	Bundesinstitut für Bevölkerungsforschung	31	58	87.1

1263	Sanofi-Aventis Deutschland GmbH	60	111	85.0
602	Ernst-Abbe-Hochschule Jena \square University	27	49	81.5
546	Jade Hochschule - Wilhelmshaven/Oldenbu	21	38	81.0
628	FOM Hochschule für Ökonomie und Manageme	76	136	78.9
5616	Leibniz-Institut zur Analyse des Biodive	137	245	78.8
785	Umweltbundesamt (UBA)	75	134	78.7
904	Bayerische Landesanstalt für Wald und Fo	23	41	78.3
195	Staatliches Museum für Naturkunde Stuttg	89	157	76.4
745	Deutsches Institut für Lebensmitteltechn	60	105	75.0
844	Bundesanstalt für Gewässerkunde	37	64	73.0
246	European Organisation for the Exploitati	21	36	71.4
5368	Translational Lung Research Center Heide	99	168	69.7
386	Westpfalz-Klinikum GmbH	25	42	68.0
5736	BioNTech SE	25	42	68.0
515	St. Hedwig-Krankenhaus Berlin	24	40	66.7
561	Hochschule RheinMain, RheinMain Universi	33	55	66.7
847	Bundesinstitut für Arzneimittel und Medi	26	43	65.4
839	Bundesamt für Strahlenschutz (BfS)	33	54	63.6
4192	Institut für Transfusionsmedizin und Imm	24	39	62.5
627	Hochschule Fresenius	38	61	60.5
752	DECHEMA Gesellschaft für Chemische Techn	28	44	57.1
598	Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	30	47	56.7
1021	Max-Planck-Institut für Stoffwechselfors	45	69	53.3
3750	Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	44	67	52.3
650	Hochschule Bremen	50	76	52.0
609	Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft Be	56	85	51.8
1155	Fraunhofer-Institut für Integrierte Syst	38	57	50.0
5551	Fraunhofer-Einrichtung für Energieinfras	28	41	46.4
24	Leibniz-Institut für Sonnenphysik (KIS)	24	35	45.8
3942	Senckenberg Naturhistorische Sammlungen	53	77	45.3
5355	CCC Comprehensive Cancer Center Mainfran	49	71	44.9
1290	Philips Deutschland GmbH	59	85	44.1
5348	Deutsches Zentrum für Lungenforschung	614	885	44.1
110	Pädagogische Hochschule Ludwigsburg	25	36	44.0
643	Fachhochschule Dortmund	30	43	43.3
617	Hochschule Heilbronn, Technik, Wirtschaf	28	40	42.9
5552	Fraunhofer-Einrichtung für Individualisi	21	30	42.9
884	Staatliche Naturwissenschaftlichen Samml	83	118	42.2
5324	Mercator Research Institute on Global Co	38	54	42.1
4625	Institut für Molekulare Biologie gGmbH	70	99	41.4
1147	Fraunhofer-Institut für Angewandte Optik	76	107	40.8
3805	Novartis International AG	42	59	40.5

Table 8: Institutions with more than 20 publications in 2022 in scp_b_202304 that decreased in publication counts by over 40% in 2023 in scp_b_202404.

Inst ID	Name	Previous pubs	Current pubs	Perc. diff.
5479	Leibniz-Zentrum Allgemeine Sprachwissens	54	32	-40.7
3442	Cochrane Deutschland Stiftung (CDS)	39	23	-41.0
1152	Fraunhofer-Institut für Lasertechnik (IL	84	46	-45.2
1169	Fraunhofer-Institut für Angewandte Polym	62	33	-46.8
670	Fachhochschule Aachen	99	52	-47.5
1058	Max-Planck-Institut für Infektionsbiolog	69	32	-53.6
5569	Leipzig Heart Institute GmbH	58	26	-55.2
1049	Max-Planck-Institut für biologische Kybe	109	44	-59.6
1094	Max-Planck-Institut für Sonnensystemfors	233	87	-62.7
1077	Max-Planck-Institut für Dynamik und Selb	431	150	-65.2
1085	Max-Planck-Institut für Biophysik	79	27	-65.8
1042	Max-Planck-Institut für medizinische For	107	35	-67.3
4429	Restkategorie Fachhochschulen	99	29	-70.7
1040	Max-Planck-Institut für Mathematik in de	193	26	-86.5

Authors: Median number of authors by Research Area and discipline

The median number of authors on a paper can be informative about patterns of collaboration and their potential implications for fractional counting. For instance, increasing levels of inter-sector or international collaboration could result in decreased publication counts for individual sectors or countries when using fractional counting. As such, understanding changes in authorship patterns can provide some insight into potential macro-level changes for entities.

We show in the left panel of Figure 18 the median number of authors per discipline in 2022 in both databases, and in the right panel the median number of authors per discipline in 2022 in the scp_b_202304 database compared to 2023 in the scp_b_202404 database.

While little change is expected to be seen in the left-hand panel of Figure 18 as the number of authors on a paper is unlikely to change between databases, differences in the right-hand panel indicate potential changes in disciplines' collaboration patterns. Disciplines for which the median number of authors changed by more than 1, based on the right-hand panel of Figure 18, are shown in Table 9.

Figure 18: Median number of authors per discipline between databases, where colour denotes the number of disciplines with this combination of median authors.

Table 9: Disciplines where the median number of authors changed by more than 1 between 2022 in scp_b_202304 and 2023 in scp_b_202404.

Discipline	Previous median authors	Current median authors	Diff.
------------	-------------------------	------------------------	-------

Source items: Percentage by Research Area and discipline

Source items refer to whether the publications on the reference list of an indexed publication are also indexed in the database, as opposed to non-source items that are not indexed. Only source items are included in citation counts and so understanding the percentage of items cited that are also source can give an indication of the depth of Scopus' coverage of a discipline. That is, if a large number of indexed items' sources are not indexed, the reverse is also likely true and a large number of citations of indexed items are also missing, which has the effect of reducing citation counts for disciplines with lower coverage, such as the arts and humanities.

The percentage of references that are source items is expected to increase over time as the database provider continues to index journals and makes efforts to improve coverage of journals from disciplines with known low coverage. The percentage is not likely to ever reach 100% however, as authors will continue to cite items outside of the scope or coverage of Scopus.

We show in the left-hand panel of Figure 19 the percentage of references that are source items per discipline in 2022 in both databases, and in the right-hand panel the percentage of references that are source items per discipline in 2022 in the scp_b_202304 database compared to 2023 in the scp_b_202404 database.

It is in the right-hand panel that the effect of recently indexed journals may become apparent, where an increase in the percentage of source items may be seen if the journal is often cited within a discipline. The disciplines with a change in the percentage of indexed references of more than five percentage points between databases, based on the right-hand panel of Figure 19, are shown in Table 10. Longer term trends can be seen in Figure 20 where we present the percentage of reference that are source items per Research Area over the last ten common years of both databases.

Figure 19: The percentage of cited items that are source items per discipline by database, where colour denotes the number of disciplines with this combination of source references.

Figure 20: The percentage of references that are source items by Research Area and database over time.

Table 10: Disciplines where the percentage of indexed references changed by 9 or more percentage points between 2022 in scp_b_202304 and 2023 in scp_b_202404.

Discipline	Prvs % source	Crrnt % source	Change
Drug Guides	60.1	70.4	10.3